

ORGANIZING THE MARKETING ACTIVITY OF THE ENTERPRISE

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ABSTRACT

Marketing is an integral element of the market economy and is one of the most modern and rapidly developing sectors of the economy. In today's complex world, we all need to understand marketing. Whether we're selling a car, looking for a job, raising money for a charity, or pitching an idea, we're marketing. We need to know what the market is, who works with it, how it works, what its needs are. Knowing how to market allows us to be smarter as consumers, whether it's buying toothpaste or buying a new car.

Introduction. When translated from English, the word marketing means "market activity", "market activity", "market research". There are many opinions about when marketing originated. One of the strict points of view is that the first elements of marketing (word of mouth, negotiation of forms of exchange) arose from the moment when mankind got rid of the isolation of the natural economy and the forms of trade appeared. However, if we admit that advertising is an important function of marketing, it is worth remembering that three thousand years ago in Babylon there were special signs promising a reward for runaway slaves: two oxen.

The most important and indispensable component of marketing in the enterprise is the sale and distribution of the product. In this process, the most difficult task from an organizational point of view is solved - delivering the produced product to the consumer. Development of the policy of distribution and sale of goods through the sales policy, organization of sales through the trade-distribution network, organization of cargo transportation and storage, determination of goods circulation, control of physical flows of the distribution system, and analysis of sales are studied.

The formation of market economy relations in the Republic of Uzbekistan, the organization of multi-ownership, the creation of market infrastructure based on them, led to a radical renewal of the economic mechanism of society. In this process, the economic relations, information system and legal environment of the trade and mass catering industry are being adapted to the conditions of the market economy.

Economic development now depends more on marketing. Uzbekistan faces huge tasks such as expanding production, increasing sales of products, increasing the volume of services,

strengthening the competitiveness of goods and services, entering foreign markets, continuously updating goods and services, and also sharply improving the quality of services.

Modern enterprises equipped with the most advanced technologies, capable of producing various types of competitive goods, have been built in Uzbekistan. The main issue is to organize the sale of goods in large quantities and to increase the volume of services, both in the republic and in foreign markets, relying on marketing technologies.

The development of the economy of the Republic of Uzbekistan based on different forms of property, based on the requirements of the market economy, is considered one of the most urgent issues of the current period. The role of small business and private entrepreneurship in the development of the national economy based on free competition is constantly increasing.

In our republic, the rapid development, promotion and support of small business and private entrepreneurship, which play an increasingly important role in ensuring economic growth, creating new jobs, solving the employment problem, and increasing the income and well-being of the population. attention is paid.

The main part. By ensuring the consistent development of small business and private entrepreneurship, we are achieving the formation and strengthening of the middle class, which is the socio-political support and foundation of our society. Therefore, small business and private entrepreneurship today are becoming a guarantee and support of social and political stability in our society, a force that actively moves our country along the path of development. Much more can be said about the obvious advantages and great opportunities of small business and private entrepreneurship.

Entrepreneurship is established, implemented and developing in all sectors and sectors of the economy. But its condition and development are not the same in all sectors.

In Uzbekistan, 60% of business entities (legal entities) are established in agriculture, 18% in trade and catering, 12% in industry and construction, and they are also developing in the service sector. The majority of individual entrepreneurs who are not legal entities are engaged in trade, public catering and some services.

One of its main tasks in the implementation of marketing in the enterprise is the control function. Marketing control is the process of ensuring that the enterprise achieves its goals.

Initial control is done by implementing formal planning and creating organizational structures. It is usually carried out in the form of specific policies, procedures and rules that are implemented before the actual start of work. Current control is based on measuring the actual results of the actions of the company (or its divisions, employees) aimed at achieving the desired results. This is done directly in the workflow.

The final control is carried out after the completion of the work or the end of the time allotted for it. Final control provides information for planning similar work and helps motivate internal and external environmental actors. The strategic direction of supervision means that supervision should reflect and support the overall priorities of the organization.

The ultimate goal of control is not to collect information, set standards and identify problems, but to solve the problems facing the enterprise. Control should be appropriate for the type of activity being controlled. Timely implementation of control. The purpose of control is to eliminate deviations from the expected development of events before taking significant measurements.

The flexibility of control is that it should adapt to the changes occurring in the external and internal environment of the enterprise, as well as the plans of the enterprise. The system must be understood and supported by people. In order for the control to be economically justified, the ratio of the costs of its implementation to the possible benefits should be much lower.

Marketing control is a comprehensive, consistent, impartial and regular study of the marketing environment, its goals, strategies or current activities in order to identify emerging problems and opportunities and to make recommendations on the action plan for improving marketing activities. Marketing control is a periodic (shift, daily, weekly, monthly, quarterly, annual) study and correction of the factors that determine the course of strategic and tactical plans.

Control allows to determine the positive and negative aspects of the organization's competitive potential. It is also important to focus on increasing control over the implementation and analysis of sales opportunities. Equally important is the control of profitability and the analysis of marketing costs, as well as long-term planning. Control in the field of sales of goods includes actual sales and their growth trends in relation to certain types of goods and their groups, individual sales departments and direct sellers, planned indicators by sales methods and types. involves strict accounting.

Implementation control provides quick information on problems that arise in the performance of assigned tasks, as well as on products, segments and markets where there are difficulties in selling goods, or on favorable marketing opportunities that have arisen and have not been considered before. includes. In the case of a decrease in sales, possible solutions to avoid a crisis situation are presented immediately. At the same time, measures are being taken to eliminate a possible shortage in the market. Analysis of the costs of marketing activities and control of the profitability of the organization affects such aspects of the activity as the profitability of individual product and their assortment groups, market segments, sales channels, advertising expenses, etc. Profitability of sales activity is usually analyzed by product groups, market segments or consumer groups.

In addition, marketing control involves the analysis of total costs for product production and sale, advertising, transportation costs, etc. Then the costs for each distribution channel are analyzed separately, profit or loss is determined. In order to determine the most useful options, adjustments are made to the organization's policy, if necessary.

Analyzing the relationship between product sales and marketing costs allows you to determine the effectiveness of marketing activities and the appropriateness of spent funds, and helps to save money in achieving marketing goals. Marketing control usually goes through four stages:

1. Setting goals and standards;
2. Determination of real values;
3. Comparison;
4. Analysis of comparison results.

The goals and objectives of marketing control include:

- determination of the level of goal achievement (analysis of deviations);
- identifying opportunities for improvement (feedback);

- checking whether the enterprise's adaptation to changes in environmental conditions corresponds to the requirements.

Control occupies an important place in marketing as one of the functions of managing production and commercial activities of the enterprise. This is, first of all, a form of targeted influence on enterprise employees, systematic control of enterprise activity, comparison of actual indicators with planned ones.

The main objects of control are the volume of sales, the volume of profits and losses, the attitude of customers to new goods and services offered by the enterprise, compliance with the planned and actual results of production and commercial activities. The adopted control system does not have to maintain control at a constant level and within strictly selected standards. Enterprise management should be flexible, and the management system should contribute to the search for new ways of managing production and commercial activities that are compatible with changes in the external environment.

In modern practice, there are four types of marketing control (according to F. Kotler): annual plan analysis, profitability control, efficiency control and strategic control.

The analysis of annual plans includes the following: sales analysis is expressed in the volume of products actually sold compared to the planned volume, the analysis also focuses on the markets with higher sales than other markets, the analysis of the market share is an indicator of the company's performance in relation to its competitors analyzed to identify strengths and weaknesses, analysis of the ratio of sales to costs - helps the organization determine the effectiveness of marketing costs and find the most optimal value.

Marketing expenses include salaries, advertising expenses, sales promotion, marketing research, etc. Increasing this indicator, increasing profits by increasing sales / reducing costs, improving capital turnover by increasing sales / reducing assets, analyzing consumer sentiment, financial analysis - for a long time, not only creating effective sales relationships, but also profitable strategies was also used for development.

Taking into account the control over the implementation of annual plans, it should be noted that this is a timely intervention in their implementation by redistributing and adjusting resources, developing additional measures and strengthening labor discipline, controlling costs.

Summary. Practice shows that during the period of recovery and formation of market relations, many enterprises kept an undifferentiated marketing strategy in their business structure. This strategy is aimed at the general interest in the buyer's needs, rather than the diversity of the company's customers in the purchase process and attitude and motivation to the product. By developing such products and marketing programs, the company can achieve its goal by satisfying the average mass of customers. An important factor in the success of enterprises using the strategy is standardization and commonality of product production. An undifferentiated marketing strategy ensures low costs in product production and sales. However, as H. Meffert noted, "this strategy is against modern marketing principles."

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